

Influence of light on expression in rice of resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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In a seedling bulk screening test to evaluate resistance to the BPH under natural conditions, daylength shorter than 5 h reduced resistance in Mudgo, IR26, ASD7, Babawee, PTB33, and Sudu Honderwala. To confirm this result, we set up an experiment with TN1 (susceptible), Baoxuan 2 and Fubao 78-2-1 (moderately resistant), IR26 and ASD7 (resistant). About 15 seeds of each variety were sown in 8-cm-long rows in 30- × 25- × 5-cm seedboxes. Treatments were laid out in a split-plot design with three replications (each seedbox served as a replication). Seedlings were thinned to 10/row 7 d after sowing (3-leaf stage) and infested with second- to third-instar BPH nymphs at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plants were grown in the phytotron at 30°C with varying light intensities and length. Damage was measured on a visual rating of 0-9.

Table 1. Damage rating of rice seedlings grown under different light regimes (8, 12, 16 h of light/d).

Variety	Damage rating ^a at							
	5,000 lux			7,000 lux			10,000 lux	
	8-h	12-h	16-h	8-h	12-h	16-h	4-h	8-h
TN1	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a
Baoxuan 2	9.0 a	8.3 a	7.7 a	9.0 a	7.0 a	3.0 c	9.0 a	3.6 b
Fubao 78-2-1	9.0 a	9.0 a	7.0 a	7.0 a	7.0 a	4.3 b	9.0 a	3.0 b
IR26	8.3 a	5.0 b	1.7 b	7.7 ab	1.7 b	1.0 d	5.0 a	1.0 b
ASD7	9.0 a	5.0 b	1.7 b	6.3 b	3.0 b	1.0 d	5.0 a	1.6 b

^a In a column, means followed by common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Effect of seedling stage on the resistance under different light conditions.

Light regime	Leaf stage	Damage rating ^a				
		TN1	Baoxuan 2	Fubao 78-2-1	IR26	ASD 7
7,000 lux, 8 h	2	9.0 a	7.0 a	7.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
	4	9.0 a	3.6 b	5.0 b	1.6 b	1.6 b
7,000 lux, 10 h	2	9.0 a	8.3 a	7.6 a	3.0 a	1.0 b
	4	9.0 a	3.0 b	3.0 b	1.0 b	1.0 b
15,000 lux, 10 h	2	9.0 a	6.3 a	6.3 a	3.0 a	1.0 b
	4	9.0 a	3.0 b	3.6 b	1.0 b	1.0 b

^a Within each light regime and in a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Resistance in IR26 and ASD7 decreased in seedlings grown under 5,000 lux for 8-12 h, 7,000 lux for 8 h, and 10,000 lux for 4 h (Table 1).

When moderately resistant and resistant plants were grown under weak

light, resistance at the 4-leaf stage was higher than at the 2-leaf stage (Table 2). When using the seedbox bulk screening test, attention should be paid to light conditions at different seedling stages. ■

Gall midge (GM) resistance in rice

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We evaluated nine rice genotypes, two potential resistance donors, and one susceptible check for resistance to GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood Mason biotype 1 during 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov).

Genotypes were tested in irrigated fields. Seedlings (27 d after seeding) were transplanted in 3-m rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing with one seedling/hill. All recommended crop management practices were followed except plant protection. Each entry was scored at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT) for

Reaction of selected rice genotypes to GM. India, 1988-89.

Designation	Cross	GM incidence ^a (% silvershoots)							
		1988				1989			
		30 DT		50 DT		30 DT		50 DT	
HB	TB	HB	TB	HB	TB	HB	TB		
BPT4220	BPT3301/WGL 26888	25	16.7	100	21.0	39	12.5	95	28.8
BPT4301	BPT3301/WGL 26888	20	10.8	90	22.4	20	12.5	85	29.1
R296-260	CR157-392/OR57-21	5	14.3	35	10.5	0	0	10	15.2
R302-103	Samridhi/IR8608-298	0	0	5	28.0	0	0	0	0
R321-108	IR36/Samridhi	0	0	85	12.7	25	11.9	60	17.7
R435-756	IR54/Surekha	0	0	10	16.7	0	0	0	0
RP2333-36-18-9	Ratna/ARC10659	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	7.7
RTN84-5-1	Phalguna/Mahsuri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTN121-1-1-1-1-1	CR57-MR1523/IR36	15	15.8	80	11.7	0	0	85	12.8
Aganni	Donor	0	0	25	5.1	0	0	0	0
ARC5984	Donor	0	0	0	0	5	7.7	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	35	21.9	100	24.8	50	14.1	100	32.6

^a HB = hill basis, TB = tiller basis, DT = days after transplanting.

number of hills with silvershoots and for number of silvershoots/infested hill. GM infestation was highest from the last week of Sep to the first week of Oct.

Only RTN84-5-1 was highly resistant to GM biotype 1 (see table). It showed no damage at 30 and 50 DT. ■